

Binuclear complexes of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} Schiff base of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde and *o*-phenylenediamine with alkali metal salts of oxygen and nitrogen containing organic acids

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Abstract : A number of stable heterobinuclear alkali metal complexes of general formula $M_aPhN.M_bL$, where $M_a = Cu^{II}$ or Ni^{II} ; $M_b = Li, Na$ or K ; $PhN = N,N'-1,2$ -phenylene-bis(2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde); $L =$ deprotonated *o*-nitrophenol (ONP), 2,4-dinitrophenol (DNP), 2,4,6-trinitrophenol (TNP) or 1-nitroso-2-naphthol (1N2N) have been synthesized using Cu^{II} or Ni^{II} metal chelates of Schiff base and alkali metal salts of ONP, DNP, TNP and 1N2N. The IR spectra suggest bonding between the Ni^{II} or Cu^{II} metal chelate and alkali metal which appear by dative bond via oxygen atoms of C–O (phenolic). Low value of molar conductance would suggest them to be non-electrolyte. These complexes are biologically active against bacteria viz. *E. coli* and *S. aureus* and fungus viz. *C. albicans* and so these may be treated as good antibacterial agents and fungicides. It was therefore, though interesting to synthesize the title compounds and examine their antimicrobial activity.

Keywords : Heterobinuclear alkali metal complex, antimicrobial studies, MIC.

Introduction

In the recent years, considerable attention has been devoted to the preparation and properties of heterobinuclear complexes, due to their potential application in bioinorganic chemistry, material science and homogenous catalysis^{1,2}. Many studies of binuclear copper(II) complexes have been reported: their magnetic properties etc. have been the subject of recent extensive investigations³⁻⁹. Several¹⁰ binuclear Cu^{II} complexes, $[Cu_2(1)(\mu-X)]$, have been prepared and characterized, the 2 : 1 Schiff base derived from 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde and 1,2-diamino-2-propanol and $X = 1,3-N_3, C_3H_3N_2$ (pyrazolate), AcO and $PhCO_2$. The Cu^{II} ions are bridged by endogenous alkoxide and bidentate exogenous bridges. Our work described herein has concentrated on developing new heterobinuclear complexes from more easily prepared metal complex as ligand and alkali metal derivative of organic acids. The condensation products have received increasing attention due to interesting structural properties and of their metal chelates and also due to their antimicrobial activity. The IR spectra suggest bonding between the Ni^{II} or Cu^{II} metal chelate and alkali metal which appear by dative bond via oxygen atoms of C–O (phenolic). The electronic spectra and magnetic moment studies show the square planar geometry of the complexes.

Results and discussion

Both the Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} metal chelate and their alkali metal adducts are coloured solid and stable at room temperature. The adducts are generally soluble in methanol, acetone, benzene and DMF but insoluble in water. Molar conductivities of complexes in DMF at 30 (± 0.5) °C and the concentration of $10^{-3} M$ (Table 1) show low value (4–12 $\Omega^{-1} cm^2 mol^{-1}$). This suggests the covalent¹¹ nature of complexes.

In the binuclear alkali metal complexes with $CuPhN$ and $NiPhN$ band (Table 2) at 1580 cm^{-1} ($CuPhN$) or 1597 cm^{-1} ($NiPhN$) was consistently shifted to higher frequency by 5–21 cm^{-1} , except $NiPhN.LiTNP$ which shows lower shifting of absorption band of metal chelate ($NiPhN$). An extra band is observed at 1535 cm^{-1} in $CuPhN$, which remains nearly same, i.e. unaffected in most of the binuclear complexes. $CuPhN.LiTNP$, $NiPhN.LiTNP$ and $NiPhN.Na1N2N$ show only one band in the region 1566–1598. This suggests, that the band observed may be due to the ν_{C-O} in the binuclear complexes, rather than $\nu_{C=N}$ ¹². The metal complex as ligand ($CuPhN$ or $NiPhN$) exhibits the ν_{C-O} (phenolic) at 1580 or 1597 cm^{-1} , which shifts towards higher energy side (with few exceptions) on complexation, indicating the coordination through the oxygen atom of C–O (phenolic)¹³.

Table 1. Analytical, magnetic and molar conductance data of the complexes

Compd. M _a PhN.M _b L	Colour	Melt./dec. trans. temp.	Molar cond.	Mag. moment	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)					Yield (%)
					C	H	N	M _a	M _b	
CuPhN.LiONP	Yellowish brown	248t	1.0	-	65.48 (65.54)	3.49 (3.53)	6.65 (6.75)	10.16 (10.20)	1.05 (1.12)	77.11
CuPhN.NaONP	Golden brown	296d	0.9	1.76	63.83 (63.90)	3.40 (3.45)	6.51 (6.58)	9.87 (9.95)	3.58 (3.60)	71.26
CuPhN.KONP	Golden brown	290d	0.8	-	62.27 (62.34)	3.28 (3.36)	6.35 (6.42)	9.65 (9.70)	5.92 (5.96)	68.37
CuPhN.LiDNP	Brownish yellow	274d	3.9	-	61.01 (61.12)	3.11 (3.15)	8.33 (8.39)	9.45 (9.51)	1.00 (1.05)	73.78
CuPhN.NaDNP	Brownish yellow	270d	2.9	-	59.61 (59.69)	3.00 (3.07)	8.11 (8.19)	9.24 (9.29)	3.34 (3.37)	77.18
CuPhN.KDNP	Brownish yellow	278md	3.6	1.79	58.25 (58.33)	2.95 (3.00)	7.93 (8.01)	9.02 (9.08)	5.53 (5.58)	73.27
CuPhN.LiTNP	Golden brown	274md	4.8	2.10	57.18 (57.26)	2.75 (2.81)	9.76 (9.82)	8.83 (8.91)	0.93 (0.98)	77.54
CuPhN.NaTNP	Orange brown	> 300	5.6	-	55.92 (56.01)	2.68 (2.75)	9.54 (9.61)	8.68 (8.72)	3.11 (3.16)	74.12
CuPhN.KTNP	Greenish brown	> 300	6.4	-	54.69 (54.80)	2.62 (2.69)	9.32 (9.40)	8.49 (8.53)	5.16 (5.24)	74.55
CuPhN.Li1N2N	Brown	248md	0.5	-	69.41 (69.46)	3.58 (3.66)	6.34 (6.40)	9.62 (9.67)	1.01 (1.07)	73.12
CuPhN.Na1N2N	Greenish brown	250md	0.6	2.15	67.68 (67.81)	3.45 (3.57)	6.14 (6.25)	9.38 (9.44)	3.36 (3.42)	76.95
CuPhN.K1N2N	Golden brown	244md	0.6	-	66.16 (66.23)	3.42 (3.49)	5.95 (6.10)	9.10 (9.22)	5.62 (5.66)	74.44
NiPhN.LiONP	Reddish brown	> 300	0.6	-	65.97 (66.05)	3.51 (3.56)	6.69 (6.80)	9.43 (9.50)	1.07 (1.13)	81.75
NiPhN.NaONP	Reddish brown	> 300	0.8	-	65.32 (64.38)	3.39 (3.47)	6.61 (6.63)	9.22 (9.26)	3.55 (3.63)	75.75
NiPhN.KONP	Reddish brown	> 300	0.6	-	62.74 (62.80)	3.35 (3.39)	6.42 (6.46)	8.96 (9.03)	5.91 (6.00)	72.73
NiPhN.LiDNP	Brownish orange	> 300	4.0	-	61.01 (61.57)	3.11 (3.17)	8.38 (8.45)	8.82 (8.86)	1.01 (1.06)	77.34
NiPhN.NaDNP	Brownish orange	> 300	5.0	-	60.03 (60.11)	3.02 (3.09)	8.19 (8.25)	8.55 (8.65)	3.33 (3.39)	70.72
NiPhN.KDNP	Brownish orange	260d	5.8	-	58.71 (58.73)	2.91 (3.02)	8.00 (8.06)	8.39 (8.45)	5.56 (5.61)	74.85
NiPhN.LiTNP	Yellowish orange	264md	7.6	-	57.51 (57.65)	2.81 (2.83)	9.78 (9.89)	8.25 (8.29)	0.92 (0.99)	74.18
NiPhN.NaTNP	Golden brown	270t	4.5	-	56.28 (56.38)	2.71 (2.76)	9.59 (9.67)	8.08 (8.11)	3.11 (3.18)	68.40
NiPhN.KTNP	Deep orange	> 300	9.8	-	55.11 (55.16)	2.61 (2.70)	9.36 (9.46)	7.85 (7.94)	5.23 (5.27)	74.69
NiPhN.Li1N2N	Yellowish brown	> 300	1.6	-	69.92 (69.97)	3.61 (3.68)	6.38 (6.44)	8.95 (9.01)	0.99 (1.07)	72.12

Table-1 (contd.)

NiPhN.Na1N2N	Orange brown	> 300	2.6	-	68.21 (68.29)	3.48 (3.59)	6.23 (6.29)	8.73 (8.79)	3.41 (3.44)	78.63
NiPhN.K1N2N	Greenish brown	> 300	3.5	-	66.62 (66.70)	3.46 (3.51)	6.05 (6.14)	8.51 (8.59)	5.65 (5.70)	7.52

The shift is expected due to maintenance of a ring current arising from electron delocalization in chelating ring. The major shift of ν_{C-O} (phenolic) to higher frequency by $\sim 21\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the complexes certainly indicating the presence of phenoxo bridge. It is therefore suggestive that the phenolic C-O bond attained a considerable amount of partial double bond character in these binuclear complexes. Assignment of the band near 1630 cm^{-1} to the conjugated C=N stretch seemed to be more possible and this is in agreement with the assignment previously made for this vibration in complexes of bisalicylaldehydetriethylenetetramine¹⁴.

The bands in the far infrared region, i.e. $470\text{--}499\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $519\text{--}571\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the binuclear complexes tentatively assigned by ν_{M-O} and ν_{M-N} modes respectively. These bands are not present in the ligand (PhN), while in metal chelates (CuPhN and NiPhN) at region $460\text{--}498\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $556\text{--}580\text{ cm}^{-1}$. These assignments are based on the assumption¹⁵ that since oxygen atom is more electronegative than nitrogen, the M-O bond tends to be more ionic than the M-N bond. Consequently M-O vibrations are accepted to appear at lower frequencies. The above data confirm the coordination of oxygen atom of phenolic group and nitrogen atom of -NO, -NO etc. to alkali metals in all the binuclear complexes.

Electronic absorption bands (Table 2) for the chelate neutral complexes of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} metals of ligand (PhN) is observed between $204\text{--}324$ and $205\text{--}340\text{ nm}$ respectively, indicating $\pi\text{-}\pi^*$ transition in aromatic ring and C=N chromophore. The bands appearing between $425\text{--}448\text{ nm}$ and 653 nm in CuPhN and NiPhN respectively, shows that there is d-d transition and charge transfer^{16,17}. Electronic spectra of all Cu^{II} bridge complexes also gave similar type of bands between $204\text{--}344\text{ nm}$ and new band in the region $394\text{--}653\text{ nm}$, indicating the formation of $\pi\text{-}\pi^*$ transition and charge transfer respectively. This suggests that there is no changes in stereochemistry of the complexes after adduct formation.

In NiPhN, absorption band of medium intensity observed at 340 nm , suggests the square planar structure of Ni^{II} with the coordination number 4. The absorption bands of binuclear alkali metal complexes (adducts) derived from NiPhN is found in the region $206\text{--}315\text{ nm}$, suggesting the similar square planar geometry of NiPhN with coordination number 4 in all the alkali metal adducts. As the coordination of Ni^{II} in NiPhN remains same in adducts, it is clear that alkali metal salts are not attached through Ni^{II}. Absorption bands in the region $207\text{--}341\text{ nm}$ and new bands in the region $365\text{--}653\text{ nm}$, indicating $\pi\text{-}\pi^*$ transition and charge transfer respectively. No absorption bands have been found in the region $700\text{--}1200\text{ nm}$ in

Table 2. Spectral data of metal chelate and their metal complexes

Compd.	Infrared spectra (cm^{-1})			Electronic spectra Diffuse reflectance (in nm)
	ν_{C-O} phenolic	ν_{M-N}	ν_{M-O}	
CuPhN	1580, 1535	556	498, 470	204, 225, 237, 324, 425, 448
CuPhN.NaONP	1601, 1539	563	499, 470	207, 224, 262, 326, 425, 448, 652
CuPhN.KDNP	1599, 1533	563, 525	470	210, 224, 344, 396, 653
CuPhN.LiTNP	1590	570	490	204, 342, 485, 652
CuPhN.Na1N2N	1601, 1533	561, 519	490, 475	219, 260, 394, 488, 652
NiPhN	1597	580	460	205, 238, 270, 340, 653
NiPhN.NaONP	1598	571, 530	490	207, 240, 324, 426, 488, 653
NiPhN.KDNP	1602, 1528	555, 520	480	206, 239, 328, 400, 653
NiPhN.LiTNP	1566	548, 522	478	207, 350, 652
NiPhN.Na1N2N	1598, 1530	570, 524	-	220, 255, 365, 652

these adducts. The absence of band in this region of electronic spectra shows that coordination number of Ni^{II} in the adducts have not been raised but it remains four with square planar structure.

The magnetic moment values for CuPhN is 1.99 B.M. and its adducts ranges from 1.76–2.15 B.M. correspond to the presence of one unpaired electron. From the results, it has been suggested that CuPhN and its adducts have square planar geometry with coordination number 4.

The magnetic moment values of NiPhN and its adducts are found to be very low (about to zero), which indicate the diamagnetism and square planar geometry. Also the stereochemistry of NiPhN and its adducts are same with coordination number 4.

Antimicrobial activity :

The heterobinuclear complexes were tested for their antibacterial activity against bacteria viz. *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and fungus viz. *Candida albicans* in DMF in the concentration range 25–200 µg ml⁻¹. The MIC results of the some of the complexes are shown in Table 3.

From above results we summarized that most of the adducts of CuPhN and NiPhN shows great degree of ac-

tivity at higher concentration against test organism (bacteria *E. coli*, *S. aureus* and fungi *Candida albicans*) and also as the concentration of these adducts increases antimicrobial activity increase gradually.

Experimental

Synthetic procedures :

Chemicals of A.R. grade have been used for synthesizing the compounds. IR spectra were recorded on FTIR spectrophotometer, Shimadzu model-8201PC in KBr. Electronic spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer-Lambda 15 UV-Vis spectrophotometer. Magnetic measurement was performed on Gouy balance.

The Schiff base of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde and *o*-phenylenediamine were prepared by refluxing these in 2 : 1 molar proportion in ethanol for 15 min. The yellow Schiff base was filtered off, washed with ethanol and dried in oven. A solution of copper(II) acetate hydrate (2.0 g) or nickel(II) acetate tetrahydrate (2.5 g) in ethanol (15 ml) was added slowly, with stirring, to a hot solution of the Schiff base (PhN, 4.16 g). The solution, upon cooling, deposited golden brown copper complex or the brownish orange nickel complex. These were filtered off, washed with ethanol and dried in electric oven.

Heterobinuclear complexes containing Cu^{II} metal and alkali metal : *N,N'*-1,2-Phenylene-bis(2-hydroxy-1-naphthalaldiminato)copper(II) [CuPhN] was taken in absolute alcohol in a conical flask and alkali metal salts of *o*-nitrophenol, dinitrophenol, trinitrophenol or 1-nitroso-2-naphthol were added to it in 1 : 1 molar proportion. The mixture was refluxed on a hot plate at 75–80 °C with stirring for 1 h. The characteristic colour adducts were precipitated in hot condition, which was filtered, washed with absolute ethanol, dried in electric oven at 80 °C and finally kept in desiccator over anhydrous CaCl₂.

Heterobinuclear complexes containing Ni^{II} metal and alkali metal : *N,N'*-1,2-Phenylene-bis(2-hydroxy-1-naphthalaldiminato)nickel(II) [NiPhN] was taken in ethanol in a conical flask and alkali metal salts of *o*-nitrophenol, dinitrophenol, trinitrophenol or 1-nitroso-2-naphthol were added to it in 1 : 1 molar proportion. The mixture was refluxed on a hot plate at 75–80 °C with stirring for 1 h. The characteristic colour adducts were precipitated in hot condition, which was filtered, washed thoroughly with absolute ethanol, dried in electric oven at 80 °C and finally kept in desiccator over anhydrous CaCl₂.

Table 3. MIC values of some of the adducts of M₂PhN with alkali metal salts of organic acids

Compd.	Concn. (µg ml ⁻¹)	Percentage inhibition		
		<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>C. albicans</i>
NiPhN.KDNP	200	100	85–90	100
	100	100	50–55	100
	50	100	50–55	85–90
	25	50–55	0	85–90
NiPhN.NaONP	200	100	100	100
	100	100	100	100
	50	100	85–90	100
	25	85–90	50–55	85–90
CuPhN.KDNP	200	85–90	100	100
	100	85–90	100	100
	50	85–90	85–90	100
	25	50–55	50–55	85–90
CuPhN.NaONP	200	100	100	100
	100	85–90	100	100
	50	85–90	100	100
	25	50–55	85–90	85–90

On the basis of quantitative analysis, general formula of binuclear alkali metal complexes with CuPhN and NiPhN have been suggested as $M_aPhN.M_bL$, where $M_a = Cu^{II}$ or Ni^{II} ; $M_b = Li, Na$ or K ; PhN = *N,N'*-1,2-phenylene-bis(2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldimine); L = deprotonated *o*-nitrophenol, 2,4-dinitrophenol, 2,4,6-trinitrophenol or 1-nitroso-2-naphthol.

The magnetic moment measurements, infrared and electronic absorption spectral studies of the adducts suggest the bonding between the *N,N'*-1,2-phenylene-bis(2-hydroxy-1-naphthaliminato)metal(II) complex, (M_aPhN) and the alkali metal is most likely to occur by dative bonding via the two phenolic oxygen atoms of the ligand. The structure and bonding of the newly prepared compounds are shown in Fig. 1.

Fig 1. Structure of the complex.

where, $M_a = Cu^{II}$ or Ni^{II} ; $M_b = Li, Na$ or K and L = deprotonated *o*-nitrophenol, 2,4-dinitrophenol, 2,4,6-trinitrophenol or 1-nitroso-2-naphthol.

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